

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ASAMOAH****FIRST NAME: EVELYN****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List of The Seven Key Concepts Discussed in the Paper

1. Selected English Language Usage (EUCLID 2019, 26 – 35)
2. Using Numbers in a Text (EUCLID 2019, 21 – 22, 52 - 53)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5 – 6)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17 – 20)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24 – 26)
6. Some Rules for Writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14 – 16)
7. Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, v – 4)

CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D provides insight to basic academic writing concepts while spelling out some ‘dos and don’ts’ as guidance for students. It emphasizes the use of the type of English adopted by the student – whether United States (US) English or United Kingdom (UK) English and the associated rules including the use of punctuation marks and periods. Furthermore, the course is concerned with plagiarism which is a grave academic offense with stringent punitive measures. Students are advised to give credit to the sources of their works to avoid plagiarizing.

2) SELECTED ENGLISH LANGUAGE USAGE

EUCLID recommends using Standard American English (SAE) rather than Standard British English (SBE) even though both options are accepted. I see this recommendation as a challenge because, in as much as I would love to follow the recommended style, I am more conversant with the SBE based on my background as coming from Ghana, a past British colony. From the coursepack, I was surprised to know how vastly American English has taken root due to several factors such as the “magnitude of higher education in America” (EUCLID 2019, 27).

In recent times, there have been series of argument on the usage of a standard English in British-colonised Ghana. Students at different educational levels have been caught in between using a ‘mixture’ of both SAE and SBE. This has caused a strong educational debate as there is a school of thought advocating for the use of only SBE based on the past relationship between Ghana and Britain. Others are also of the view that students can use SAE as long as the students are consistent.

Furthermore, I find the explanation and examples given on the usage of ‘comma’ to be less explicit. There is no difference between examples one and two thus making it difficult to comprehend what the author was trying to point out (EUCLID 2019, 20). Perhaps, example two should read “My favorite types of sandwiches... roast beef and turkey club”, where there is no final ‘comma’ before the conjunction ‘and’.

a) Using Numbers in a Text

Knowing when numbers should be written out as numerals or spelled out in a text is very vital in essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 21). However, this has been my biggest problem as I have not been able to master the art of deciphering when to write it as a number or spell it out. Apart from calendrical dates which I have no problem writing them out in figures, I have dilemma with regard to writing other numbers. Sometimes, when writing percentages, I get confused as to whether I should write them in words as in “twelve per cent” or “12%”. I therefore intend to master the usage of numbers in essay writing to enable me to produce an unambiguous work as well as avoid committing unpardonable blunders.

b) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is considered a grave offense in academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 5). Therefore, it is important that writers give credit to another author when they cite that author’s work in an essay. To promote academic fairness, students are advised to avoid plagiarism and to give credit to someone’s work. Plagiarism is a very dicey issue to handle because it demands a lot of circumspection. What I find intriguing is the issue of paraphrasing when citing a work. I recall using synonyms in one of my essays to replace certain words of someone’s work during my graduate studies and trying to own it as if I originated them, believing that it would beat plagiarism. Unfortunately, I could not escape being caught in the plagiarism web and had to face the consequences. Luckily for me, it was work in progress and so I had to rewrite the whole section. Good academic work is characterized by ethics and, therefore, unethical not to give credit to an idea used by another person.

Writers must quote only if the quote is significant for the essay:

When you attribute views to the person whose ideas you are addressing, indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting relevant passages. But you need not include quotations. As a general rule, you should only quote a passage if the passage plays an important role in the paper (say, it is a passage that you will want to be able to refer back to at various points in the argument), or if you

think that there is some controversy about whether the philosopher actually held the view you are attributing to him or her (EUCLID 2019, 15).

The above quote is self-explanatory, and it has enlightened me on the significance of quoting. I am now better informed that writers are expected to quote only when the quotation is relevant to their arguments.

i) *Literature Review*

I found the literature review section very interesting and helpful. The right usage of apostrophe before or after ‘S’ in the possessive, for instance, brings to mind an argument I had with a friend recently concerning “Mothers’ Day”. This friend wrote a letter to her mother wishing her a “Happy Mother’s Day”. I argued that she was supposed to have written it with the apostrophe after the ‘S’ since it was a day signifying the celebration of all mothers worldwide and not one particular mother. However, she was of the view that hers was the right way to write it. Another interesting part of this section is the proper use of “its” and “it’s” (EUCLID 2019, 19). This has been my bane because I am not able to choose the right one in most of my written sentences and, therefore, I need to control the usage of the two.

Besides the above-mentioned concern, I found the examples given under the usage of “comma” to be ambiguous (EUCLID 2019, 20). There was no difference between example one and example two regarding the appropriate placement of “comma”. Perhaps example two should have read “My favorite types of sandwiches are... and jelly, cream cheese, roast beef and turkey”. In this case, the final comma after the “roast beef” is removed in accordance with the given explanation to the example.

ii) *Style Guide*

Although writers could choose to write without any style guide, it is prudent to adopt a style guide to enable readers to easily comprehend the text. My first time of hearing the word “Turabian” was in the ACA 401D Course pack. Even though I have used the Chicago Manual of Style before, little did I know that it was also called “Turabian”. Surprisingly, quite a number of my work colleagues also did not know what “Turabian” was. To me, it is a great pleasure to acquire more knowledge and knowing this word has further enhanced my academic vocabulary.

The EUCLID Style Guide demonstrates that style goes beyond just using punctuations and grammar. “For any writer...a style guide should be an invaluable tool”. This means that every writer is expected to employ a style guide in their works. Style guide does not only embody a chosen referencing style, but also incorporates more profound areas such as font size and sentence lengths. The EUCLID style guide teaches me to use active rather than passive voice as well as correct spelling in accordance with the SAE or SBE (EUCLID 2019, 25).

iii) *Some Rules for Writing Papers*

In writing an essay, it is important that the writer states their main thesis in the introduction. This helps in drawing readers' attention to what the paper seeks to discuss or analyse. Moreover, stating the main thesis at the beginning helps in steering the writer's thoughts while guarding his focus. As a writer, I must state my argument clearly and eschew ambiguity (EUCLID 2019, 14).

One specific thing I underlined in this section is that I must read my paper out loud for, "writing that does not sound right will not read right" (EUCLID 2019,16). This practice, I must attest, has helped me in diverse ways especially when preparing for public presentations. Sometimes I am tempted to skip it, believing that everything I have written down is perfect. However, after reading the script or power point headings aloud, I usually observe and correct some grave mistakes.

iv) *Basics for Essay Writing*

In writing an academic essay, it is important that, as a student, I research the topic and write down notes from the research. This will help facilitate the analyses I make as well as give credit to the source of my research. It is also important that I start preparing early to avoid last minute preparation since "you cannot write a successful essay unless you give yourself enough time to read...and write" (EUCLID 2019, 1). In so doing, I must draw up a preliminary essay plan and start working on drafts until I produce a final paper that addresses my thesis questions.

3) CONCLUSION

Academic writing takes into consideration certain styles that need to be followed to facilitate clarity of ideas and arguments. It provides an avenue for the writer to communicate their assertions while giving credit to the works of other authors whose works they have cited. EUCLID style of academic writing is tailored towards allowing students to follow a specific style that improves their knowledge of both spoken and written English. One particular aspect of the ACA-401D coursepack that I will not forget is the issue of plagiarism which constitutes an academic offense.

Furthermore, in writing academic essays, I have learnt that it pays to start preparing early and to write down notes while conducting the research. As part of the preparation, I must have series of drafts in order to obtain a clear and final paper that answers my thesis question and devoid of ambiguity. It does not only end at the final paper but continues with reading the essay aloud in order to further identify any nuances.

REFERENCES

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